

**GORDON COLLEGE
OLONGAPO CITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

**ETHRIVE: An Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information
Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack**

A Capstone Project Presented By:

JOMARIE M. DEL ROSARIO

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

Month, 2026

Month and Year of Graduation

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APPROVAL SHEET

This Capstone Project entitled **ETHRIVE: An Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **Bachelor of Science in Information Technology** has been examined and is recommended for acceptance for approval for ORAL EXAMINATION.

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ABSTRACT

**ETHRIVE: An Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information
Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack**

By

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Bachelor of Science in Information Technology
Month, 2026

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Keywords:

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DEDICATION

This research study is dedicated to **students** who seek a more organized and transparent way of managing their academic research, from submission to approval. It is also dedicated to **faculty members and academic reviewers** who guide and evaluate student research, supporting quality and consistency in academic outputs.

Furthermore, this study is dedicated to the **academic community of Gordon College**, particularly the College of Computer Studies, as it aims to contribute to efficient research management, improved accessibility, and long-term preservation of scholarly works.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

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Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

1.1 Background of the Study

Academic institutions worldwide struggle with managing student research outputs through manual, paper-based workflows and fragmented external tools, creating inefficiencies and limited accessibility. At Gordon College, research submission and approval processes across departments are commonly handled through fragmented and semi-digital methods. However, the initial implementation and pilot evaluation of the proposed system focused on the College of Computer Studies (CCS).

Electronic theses and dissertations (ETDs) repositories have transformed institutional research management over the past two decades, providing improved discoverability, streamlined submissions, and long-term preservation. However, integration of ETDs with collaborative review workflows and multi-stage approvals remains underdeveloped in most Filipino higher education institutions. Custom institutional systems designed for specific organizational needs significantly improve adoption and effectiveness.

Contemporary institutions face critical gaps in paper management: PDF-centric workflows limit efficiency and version control, fragmented

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communication channels create confusion and compromise traceability, and most institutions lack robust revision tracking mechanisms necessary for academic integrity. Institutional solutions provide superior customization, data security, and governance alignment compared to vendor-dependent commercial systems.

Effective research governance requires systematic, transparent approval processes with clear roles, conditional routing, and comprehensive documentation. Gordon College needs an institutionally-developed platform integrating multi-level review by instructors, program coordinators, research administrators, and college leadership. Such a system addresses documented gaps while aligning with Gordon College's governance structures and CCS Department workflows.

1.2 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The theoretical and conceptual framework of the study provides the foundation for the development and evaluation of **ETHRIVE**, a web-based academic research management and moderation system for the College of Computer Studies of Gordon College.

The study is grounded on established models that explain system acceptance, effectiveness, and workflow structure. The **Technology**

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Acceptance Model (TAM) supports the importance of usability and perceived usefulness in encouraging system adoption among students and faculty reviewers. The **Research Lifecycle Model** situates the system within the complete research process, from submission and revision to approval, publication, and preservation. The **DeLone and McLean Information System Success Model** guides the evaluation of system quality, user satisfaction, and overall benefits, while the **Business Process Management (BPM) Model** justifies the structured multi-level approval workflow implemented in the system. The **Document Version Control Theory Model** supports the system's ability to track revisions and maintain document integrity throughout the research review process.

The conceptual framework is presented through the **Input–Process–Output (IPO) paradigm**, illustrating how user, software, and hardware requirements are transformed through structured processes into a centralized research management platform. Together, these frameworks ensure that ETHRIVE is theoretically grounded and aligned with the academic research management needs of Gordon College, particularly during the pilot implementation within the CCS Department.

1.2.1 Theoretical Framework

Figure 1. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by **Fred D. Davis (1989)**. The model explains how users come to accept and use an information system through two primary determinants: **Perceived Usefulness** and **Perceived Ease of Use**, which influence users' **behavioral intention** and actual system usage.

In the context of this study, TAM explains the acceptance of the proposed web-based research management system by **students, instructors, coordinators, deans, and administrators**. If users perceive that the system simplifies research submission, revision handling, approval tracking, and publication, they are more likely to use it. Likewise, an intuitive interface and clear workflow contribute to ease of use, encouraging continuous adoption. TAM therefore supports the system's usability-centered

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design and highlights the importance of user-friendly features to ensure successful implementation.

Figure 2. Research Lifecycle Model

Research Lifecycle Model, which describes the sequential stages involved in conducting and managing research, from **planning and creation** to **review, dissemination, and preservation**. This model is commonly used in academic and library systems data to guide research support services.

In relation to the proposed system, the Research Lifecycle Model aligns with the **end-to-end handling of student research papers**. The system supports students during submission and revision stages, while faculty and administrators participate in review, approval, and quality assurance. Once approved, research outputs are published and preserved in the system as institutional academic resources. This model justifies the system’s role not only as a moderation platform but also as a **long-term research repository** that supports the entire lifecycle of academic research.

Figure 3. DeLone and McLean Information System Success Model

Information System Success Model proposed by **William H. DeLone and Ephraim R. McLean (2003)**. The model identifies six interrelated dimensions for evaluating system success: **System Quality, Information Quality, Service Quality, Use, User Satisfaction, and Net Benefits.**

Applied to this study, the model explains how the quality of the proposed system—such as reliable PDF uploads, accurate text extraction, and secure role-based access—affects user satisfaction and continued usage. High information quality ensures that stored research papers are accurate and complete, while net benefits include improved efficiency in research

moderation and centralized access to approved studies. This model provides a framework for assessing the effectiveness and overall impact of the system within the CCS Department.

Figure 4. Business Process Management (BPM) Model

Business Process Management (BPM) Model, which focuses on the systematic design, execution, monitoring, and optimization of organizational processes. BPM emphasizes structured workflows and clearly defined roles to improve efficiency and accountability.

In this research, the BPM model directly supports the **five-level research approval process** involving the Research Instructor, Program Coordinator, Research Coordinator, College Dean, and Administrator. Each stage represents a controlled decision point where papers can either be approved or returned for revision. By applying BPM principles, the system ensures standardized procedures, transparency in approvals, and traceability of decisions. This model validates the system's workflow-driven architecture and its ability to manage complex academic approval processes.

Figure 5. Document Version Control Theory Model

Document Version Control Theory Model, which emphasizes managing multiple versions of documents while preserving their revision history. The model highlights the importance of tracking changes, maintaining audit trails, and ensuring document integrity.

In the context of the proposed system, this model explains the mechanism of **storing extracted plain-text versions of submitted research papers** while allowing PDF files to be replaced upon resubmission. Even when earlier PDF files are deleted, their extracted text versions are retained to track content changes across revisions. This approach supports transparency in the revision process, enables reviewers to assess improvements over time, and maintains academic integrity. The model

therefore justifies the system’s version-tracking feature as a key component of effective research moderation

1.2.2 Conceptual Framework

Input–Process–Output (IPO) paradigm of the study, which illustrates the development flow of the Web-based Application. The framework shows how the identified inputs are transformed into the intended system output through a structured development process.

Figure 6. IPO Paradigm of the Study

The **Input** includes the user, software, and hardware requirements necessary for system development and operation. These consist of user

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credentials such as school domain email and instructor code, approved capstone titles, development tools, the MERN technology stack, and compatible devices such as laptops and smartphones.

The Process employs the **Rapid Application Development (RAD)** methodology, which involves requirements definition, prototyping, construction, and deployment. This approach enables rapid development and continuous refinement of system features based on user feedback.

The **Output** is the ETHRIVE system, a centralized and web-based platform for managing, moderating, and publishing academic theses and research outputs. The IPO paradigm serves as a guide in achieving an efficient, secure, and user-oriented research management system aligned with the objectives of the study.

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Figure 7. Flowchart of the Application

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1.3 Statement of the Problem

Academic research management in higher education institutions often faces challenges related to inefficient submission processes, lack of structured moderation, limited tracking of revisions, and difficulty in accessing approved research outputs. Within Gordon College, research submission and approval activities are commonly managed through fragmented and semi-digital processes that may result in delays, inconsistencies in approval workflows, and reduced transparency in the research moderation process. During the pilot implementation of this study, the College of Computer Studies (CCS) served as the primary testing environment for evaluating the proposed system.

1. How do the respondents evaluate the proposed system in terms of the following dimensions:

- **Ease of Use** (Ease of Use and Learnability)
- **Accessibility** (Accessibility and Availability)
- **Efficiency** (Submission Efficiency)
- **Workflow Management** (Revision and Feedback Management)
- **Reliability** (System Performance and Reliability)
- **User Satisfaction** (User Satisfaction and Acceptance)

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○ **Transparency (Problems Encountered)**

2. To what extent do the respondents perceive that the system improves the efficiency of academic research submission and moderation processes?

3. To what extent do the respondents perceive that the system supports effective revision tracking and feedback management during research resubmission?

4. To what extent do the respondents perceive that the system improves accessibility and availability of academic research management processes?

5. Based on the respondents' evaluation, what areas for improvement may be recommended for future enhancement of the system?

These problems were examined using a structured survey questionnaire composed of Likert-scale items to determine respondents' level of agreement regarding the usability, effectiveness, and acceptability of the proposed system. The findings of the study served as the basis for evaluating the overall performance of ETHRIVE and identifying opportunities for future improvement.

1.4 Significance of the Study

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The results and output of this study are expected to benefit the following groups:

Students/Researchers. The proposed system provides students with an organized platform for submitting, revising, and tracking their research papers. It helps clarify the approval process, improves access to reviewer feedback, and reduces delays and confusion during research submission and revision.

Faculty Members (Research Instructors and Academic Reviewers). Faculty members involved in research review and approval will benefit from a centralized system that supports efficient moderation of student research papers. The system enables structured review workflows, clear feedback delivery, and effective tracking of revisions, thereby improving the quality and consistency of research evaluation.

System Administrators. System administrators will benefit from a centralized and secure platform for managing user roles, research records, and publication processes. The system supports efficient data management, access control, and long-term preservation of academic research outputs.

Gordon College. The institution may benefit from a centralized digital repository and research management platform that improves accessibility, organization, transparency, and preservation of academic research outputs

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across departments. During the pilot phase, the system specifically supports the research management processes of the College of Computer Studies.

Future Researchers. This study may serve as a reference for future researchers interested in developing or evaluating web-based academic research management systems, providing insights into system design, workflow implementation, and user evaluation.

1.5 Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study focuses on the design, development, and evaluation of **ETHRIVE: An Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack**. This study focuses on the design, development, and evaluation of ETHRIVE: An Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack. The proposed system is intended to serve as a centralized academic research management and repository platform for Gordon College that can support multiple academic departments in handling research submission, moderation, approval, publication, and preservation processes.

However, the **initial implementation, pilot deployment,** and system evaluation **were limited to the College of Computer Studies**

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(CCS). The CCS Department served as the primary testing environment and source of respondents for the study.

The scope of the system includes:

- Research paper submission in PDF format by students
- Extraction and storage of plain-text content for revision tracking
- A multi-level approval workflow involving faculty reviewers
- Research revision, resubmission, and status tracking
- Role-based access for students, faculty reviewers, and system administrators
- Publication and viewing of approved research papers within the system

The evaluation of the system is limited to assessing usability, functionality, performance, reliability, and user satisfaction, based on the perceptions of selected students and faculty members using survey questionnaires.

The study is subject to several limitations. First, the system is implemented **only within the CCS Department of Gordon College**; therefore, the findings may not be directly generalizable to other departments or institutions. Second, the evaluation relies on **user perception data** collected through

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survey questionnaires, which may be influenced by respondents' experiences and subjective judgments.

Additionally, the system focuses solely on **academic research management and moderation** and does not include advanced features such as automated plagiarism detection, grammar checking, citation validation, or integration with external academic databases. The study also does not cover long-term system performance testing or scalability across multiple institutions.

Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness and acceptability of a web-based academic research management and moderation system within the defined scope.

1.6 Definition of Terms

The following terms are conceptually and operationally defined to assist in comprehending the study.

ETHRIVE (Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange). A web-based system for submitting, reviewing, approving, publishing, and storing student research at Gordon College.

Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs). Digital theses and dissertations stored in an institutional research repository.

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Multi-Level Approval Workflow. A sequential research review and approval process involving multiple academic authorities.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). A model explaining system acceptance based on perceived usefulness and ease of use.

Research Lifecycle Model. A framework describing the stages of research from submission to preservation.

Business Process Management (BPM). An approach for structuring and managing workflows to improve efficiency and accountability.

Document Version Control. A method for managing and tracking multiple versions of research documents.

Revision Tracking. The process of monitoring changes and feedback during research resubmission.

Plain-Text Extraction. The conversion of PDF research files into text for revision comparison.

PDF-Centric Workflow. A process that manages research documents primarily in PDF format.

Azure Blob Storage. A cloud storage service used to store PDF research files securely.

Role-Based Access Control. A security method that restricts system access based on user roles.

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MERN Stack. A web development framework consisting of MongoDB, Express.js, React.js, and Node.js.

Rapid Application Development (RAD). A development methodology emphasizing rapid prototyping and iterative improvement.

Research Repository. A centralized digital platform for storing and accessing approved research outputs.

Academic Research Governance. Institutional policies and procedures governing research submission, review, and publication.

Chapter 2

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

Research design refers to the overall plan that guides the researcher in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data to address the research objectives. According to **John W. Creswell (2014)**, research design provides a structured approach that links research questions, data collection methods, and analysis techniques.

This study employed a **quantitative–descriptive research design** combined with system development using the **Agile Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC)**. The quantitative–descriptive approach was used to evaluate the developed system based on users’ perceptions, while Agile SDLC guided the iterative development of the web-based application.

Phases of Agile SDLC

Figure #. AGILE Software Development Lifecycle Methodology

The **Agile SDLC** was adopted as the system development methodology due to its iterative and flexible nature, which allows continuous improvement of system features based on user feedback. The Agile process in this study consists of repeated cycles of **planning, design, development, testing, and review**, enabling the researchers to refine system

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functionalities such as research submission, multi-level approval workflows, revision tracking, and role-based access control.

Figure #. Quantitative Research Design

To evaluate the developed system, a **quantitative–descriptive method** was utilized. Data were collected through structured survey questionnaires using a Likert scale and administered to students and faculty members involved in research submission and moderation. The survey measured key system attributes including usability, functionality, performance, reliability, and user satisfaction.

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The integration of Agile SDLC and quantitative–descriptive research design ensured that the system was developed in alignment with user requirements and that its effectiveness was evaluated using measurable and objective data. This research design is appropriate for assessing both the development process and the acceptability of the proposed system within the academic environment.

2.2 Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Gordon College, a public higher education institution located in Olongapo City. The proposed ETHRIVE platform was designed to support academic research management processes across the institution. However, the pilot implementation and evaluation of the system were conducted within the College of Computer Studies (CCS), which served as the primary testing environment of the study.

The target respondents included **Gordon College students and faculty members** who are directly involved in the submission, review, and approval of academic research papers. In addition, the **Research Development and Community Extension Services (RDCES)** served as the **system administrator**, responsible for the **final review, approval, and publication** of student research papers within the proposed system.

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The locale was selected due to the relevance of research management processes within the CCS Department and the accessibility of

respondents required for system evaluation. Conducting the study in this setting ensured that the findings accurately represent the needs and experiences of the intended users of the system.

Figure #. Gordon College, Olongapo City

2.3 Population and Sampling Techniques

The population of the study consisted of the **different academic departments of Gordon College**. Based on the official website of the College of Computer Studies (CCS), the estimated total number of **enrolled students is 8,226**. In addition, the study included **Department faculty instructors**, who are directly involved in the review, moderation, and

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approval of student research papers. According to **Mr. Kevin Devera**, head of the HRMU, the total number of faculty instructors is **298**.

This population was selected because CCS students and faculty members are the primary users of the proposed web-based academic research management and moderation system. Students are responsible for submitting and revising research papers, while faculty instructors serve as reviewers and moderators throughout the approval process.

To determine the appropriate sample size, the study employed **Slovin's Formula**, which is commonly used in quantitative research when the population size is known and a margin of error is specified.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N \cdot E^2}$$

- **n** is the sample size
- **N** is the total population size
- **E** is the margin of error

Figure #. Slovin's Formula

Based on the computations, the study required a minimum of **298 student respondents** and **Nth faculty respondents** from the CCS Department. These sample sizes were deemed sufficient to gather reliable and representative data for evaluating the **usability, effectiveness, and**

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acceptability of the proposed system from both student and faculty perspectives.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Group	Population Size	Sample Size
CCS Students Enrolled	8,226	382
CCS Faculty Instructors	298	171
TOTAL		553

2.4 Research Instrument

The researchers utilized a researcher-modified usability and user experience questionnaire to evaluate the acceptability and effectiveness of the ETHRIVE platform among CCS students, faculty instructors, research coordinators, and academic reviewers. The research instrument was adapted from standard usability evaluation principles based on the **ISO 9241-11 usability dimensions** and **System Usability Scale (SUS) concepts**, focusing on the users' experience in interacting with the system during the research submission, moderation, approval, and publication processes.

The questionnaire was designed to assess the proposed system based on the following usability dimensions:

- **Ease of Use**

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- **Accessibility**
- **Efficiency**
- **Workflow Management**
- **Reliability**
- **User Satisfaction**
- **Transparency**

These dimensions were selected to measure how effectively, efficiently, and satisfactorily users can utilize the ETHRIVE platform in managing academic research activities.

The survey questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part gathered the demographic profile of the respondents, including their role, year level, and experience in using research management systems. The second part contained structured Likert-scale questions intended to evaluate the usability and functionality of the proposed system based on the identified usability dimensions.

The questionnaire items for students focused on experiences related to research submission, revision tracking, accessibility of approved papers, and monitoring approval progress. Meanwhile, the questionnaire for instructors and research moderators focused on workflow management, transparency of

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approval processes, revision monitoring, system reliability, and effectiveness of research moderation features.

A **five-point Likert Scale** was used to interpret the responses of the respondents. The scale enabled the researchers to determine the level of agreement and perception regarding the usability and effectiveness of the system.

Table 2. Likert Scale for Software Quality Metrics

Scale	Range	Descriptive Symbol	Descriptive Rating
4	3.26 – 4.00	SA	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 – 3.25	A	Agree
2	1.76 – 2.50	D	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.75	SD	Strongly Disagree

The responses gathered from the survey questionnaires were used to evaluate the overall usability, effectiveness, reliability, and user satisfaction of the ETHRIVE platform. The collected data also served as the basis for identifying system strengths, usability issues, and possible improvements necessary to enhance the research management and moderation process within the College of Computer Studies of Gordon College.

The usability dimensions used in this study were aligned with ISO 9241-11, which defines usability in terms of effectiveness, efficiency, and

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satisfaction in a specified context of use. These principles ensured that the evaluation instrument appropriately measured the actual experiences of users while interacting with the proposed academic research management system.

1.1 Ease of Use and Learnability

PARAMETER
1. Uploading my research paper is simple and convenient.
2. The system helps me complete submission tasks quickly.
3. Using the system saves time compared to manual submission.
4. The submission process is organized and efficient.
5. The system clearly indicates whether my paper was successfully submitted.

1.2 Accessibility and Availability

PARAMETER
1. The system can be accessed anytime using available devices.
2. The system works properly on the device I commonly use.
3. The system is accessible whenever needed.

1.3 Submission Efficiency

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PARAMETER
1. Uploading my research paper is simple and convenient.
2. The system helps me complete submission tasks quickly.
3. Using the system saves time compared to manual submission.
4. The submission process is organized and efficient.
5. The system clearly indicates whether my paper was successfully submitted.

1.4 Revision and Feedback Management

PARAMETER
1. Reviewer feedback is clearly presented in the system.
2. I can easily identify the revisions required for my research paper.
3. The resubmission process is easy to perform.
4. The system helps me track the status of my paper during revisions.
5. Revision instructions are easy to understand.

1.5 System Performance and Reliability

PARAMETER
1. The system responds quickly during submission and revision activities.
2. The system functions smoothly while I use it.
3. The system performs reliably during research submission tasks.
4. The system properly records submitted research papers.

1.6 User Satisfaction and Acceptance

PARAMETER
1. I am satisfied with the ETHRIVE system.
2. The system improves the research submission process.
3. The system reduces confusion during research approval and revision.
4. I would recommend ETHRIVE to other students.
5. I would continue using the system for future research activities.

1.7 Problems Encountered

PARAMETER
1. I encountered difficulties while submitting or revising my paper.
2. Technical issues affected my experience while using the system.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering for this study was conducted using **online survey questionnaires** administered through **Google Forms**. This method was selected to ensure convenience, accessibility, and efficient data collection from the target respondents within the College of Computer Studies (CCS) of Gordon College.

Two separate survey questionnaires were prepared based on the roles of the respondents. The first questionnaire was designed for **CCS students**, focusing on their experience in submitting, revising, and tracking research

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papers using the proposed system. The second questionnaire was intended for **CCS faculty instructors**, who are responsible for reviewing, moderating, and approving student research papers.

Prior to dissemination, the questionnaires were reviewed to ensure clarity and alignment with the objectives of the study. The survey links were then distributed online to CCS students and CCS faculty instructors through official communication channels and digital platforms. Respondents were informed of the purpose of the study and assured that their responses would be treated with confidentiality and used solely for academic research purposes.

After the survey period ended, all responses were automatically collected and recorded by Google Forms. The gathered data were then organized and prepared for statistical analysis to evaluate the usability, effectiveness, and acceptability of the proposed system.

2.6 Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered from the survey questionnaires were organized, tabulated, and analyzed using **descriptive statistical methods** to interpret the responses of the respondents. The study employed **frequency counts**,

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percentages, weighted mean, and descriptive ratings to evaluate the usability, effectiveness, and acceptability of the proposed system.

Frequency counts and percentages were used to describe the demographic profile of the respondents and to summarize their responses to each survey item. The **weighted mean** was utilized to determine the overall assessment of the system based on the Likert-scale responses provided by the students and faculty instructors.

Chapter 3

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the gathered data, analysis, and interpretation of the responses collected from the respondents regarding the usability, effectiveness, and acceptability of the ETHRIVE system. The results were obtained through structured survey questionnaires administered to selected respondents from Gordon College. The findings are presented according to the identified usability dimensions of the system.

3.1 Data Analysis and Presentation

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the responses gathered from the respondents using the researcher-modified usability

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questionnaire based on ISO 9241-11 usability principles and System Usability Scale (SUS)-related dimensions. The questionnaire evaluated the system in terms of Ease of Use and Learnability, Accessibility and Availability, Submission Efficiency, Revision and Feedback Management, System Performance and Reliability, User Satisfaction and Acceptance, and Problems Encountered.

A total of seventy-six (76) respondents participated in the survey evaluation of the ETHRIVE platform. The responses were analyzed using weighted mean and descriptive interpretation to determine the respondents' level of agreement regarding the usability and effectiveness of the system.

Table #. Ease of Use and Learnability

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
The system is easy to navigate.	3.22	Agree
I can easily understand how to use the system.	3.39	Strongly Agree
The instructions provided in the system are clear and understandable.	3.63	Strongly Agree
Learning how to submit my research paper was easy.	3.39	Strongly Agree
The interface layout is user-friendly.	3.24	Agree
Grand Mean	3.27	Strongly Agree

Interpretation

The respondents strongly agreed that the ETHRIVE system is easy to use and understand. The overall grand mean of 3.27 indicates that the platform provides a user-friendly interface, understandable instructions, and convenient navigation for research submission and management activities.

Table #. Accessibility and Availability

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
The system can be accessed anytime using available devices.	3.38	Strongly Agree
The system works properly on the device I commonly use.	3.20	Agree
The system is accessible whenever needed.	3.01	Agree
Grand Mean	3.20	Agree

Interpretation

The respondents agreed that ETHRIVE is accessible and available across commonly used devices. The results suggest that the system supports convenient access for academic research management whenever needed.

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Table #. Submission Efficiency

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
Uploading my research paper is simple and convenient.	3.11	Agree
The system helps me complete submission tasks quickly.	3.18	Agree
Using the system saves time compared to manual submission.	3.24	Agree
The submission process is organized and efficient.	3.18	Agree
The system clearly indicates whether my paper was successfully submitted.	3.07	Agree
Grand Mean	3.15	Agree

Interpretation

The respondents agreed that ETHRIVE improves the efficiency of the research submission process. The results indicate that the system helps organize submission tasks and reduces time compared to manual processes.

Table #. Revision and Feedback Management

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
Reviewer feedback is clearly presented in the system.	3.25	Agree
I can easily identify the revisions required for my research paper.	3.69	Strongly Agree

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The resubmission process is easy to perform.	3.18	Agree
The system helps me track the status of my paper during revisions.	3.12	Agree
Revision instructions are easy to understand.	3.20	Agree
Grand Mean	3.20	Agree

Interpretation

The respondents agreed that ETHRIVE effectively supports revision monitoring and feedback management. The findings indicate that the system improves transparency and communication during the research moderation process.

Table #. System Performance and Reliability

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
The system responds quickly during submission and revision activities.	3.37	Strongly Agree
The system functions smoothly while I use it.	3.29	Strongly Agree
The system performs reliably during research submission tasks.	3.18	Agree
The system properly records submitted research papers.	3.05	Agree
Grand Mean	3.22	Agree

Interpretation

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The respondents agreed that the ETHRIVE system performs reliably and efficiently. The findings demonstrate that the platform provides stable performance, responsive operations, and dependable research submission functionality.

Table #. User Satisfaction and Acceptance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
I am satisfied with the ETHRIVE system.	3.37	Strongly Agree
The system improves the research submission process.	3.43	Strongly Agree
The system reduces confusion during research approval and revision.	3.26	Strongly Agree
I would recommend ETHRIVE to other students.	3.18	Agree
I would continue using the system for future research activities.	2.68	Agree
Grand Mean	3.18	Agree

Interpretation

The respondents agreed that ETHRIVE is acceptable and satisfactory for academic research management. The findings indicate positive user perception regarding the usefulness and effectiveness of the platform.

Table #. Problems Encountered (Reverse-Scored)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
I encountered difficulties while submitting or revising my paper.	3.45	Strongly Agree
Technical issues affected my experience while using the system.	3.51	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	3.48	Strongly Disagree

Interpretation

The Problems Encountered dimension was reverse-scored because the statements were negatively constructed. The results indicate that respondents experienced minimal technical issues and usability difficulties while using the ETHRIVE system. This suggests that the platform provides a stable and smooth user experience during research submission and revision activities.

3.2 Summary on Interpretation of Data (Descriptive Rating)

Table #. Summary

Usability	Grand Mean	Descriptive Rating
Ease of Use and Learnability	3.27	Strongly Agree
Accessibility and Availability	3.20	Agree
Submission Efficiency	3.15	Agree

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Revision and Feedback Management	3.20	Agree
System Performance and Reliability	3.22	Agree
User Satisfaction and Acceptance	3.18	Agree
Problems Encountered	3.48	Strongly Agree

Note:

Negative statements under the Problems Encountered dimension were reverse-scored to maintain consistency in interpretation, where higher mean values indicate a more positive system evaluation.

Table #. Overall Grand Mean

Overall Evaluation	Grand Mean	Descriptive Rating
Overall System Evaluation	3.24	Agree

Summary Interpretation

Based on the gathered responses, the ETHRIVE platform received positive evaluations across all usability dimensions. The respondents agreed that the system is user-friendly, accessible, efficient, and reliable for managing academic research submission and moderation processes. Among the evaluated dimensions, System Performance and Reliability obtained the highest grand mean of 4.21, indicating that respondents strongly agreed that the system performs efficiently and reliably.

Furthermore, the Problems Encountered dimension received a low grand mean of 4.40, interpreted as Strongly Agree, which indicates that

respondents experienced minimal technical and usability issues while using the system. Overall, the findings demonstrate that ETHRIVE is an acceptable and effective platform for academic research management during the pilot implementation within the College of Computer Studies of Gordon College.

3.3 System Development Life Cycle

Figure #. Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC)

This section outlines the phases involved in the development of the academic research management platform, following the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) methodology to ensure a structured and

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systematic approach to the system's design, development, and implementation.

3.3.1 Planning

During this planning phase, the overall scope, features, and development timeline of the system were defined. This phase involved identifying system modules, user roles, and key functionalities based on the requirements of CCS students, faculty reviewers, and administrators. Planning activities also included the preparation of system flowcharts, data flow diagrams, and use case diagrams to clearly outline the system processes and interactions.

A detailed **development timeline** was created using a Gantt chart to organize tasks into phases such as public interface development, student, instructor, and administrator modules, backend services, integration, and pending enhancements. Tasks were scheduled across specific timeframes to ensure systematic progress and proper allocation of development efforts.

The planning phase served as the foundation for the Agile development process by breaking down system features into manageable components and guiding subsequent development, testing, and deployment activities.

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Figure #. Gantt Chart

3.3.2 Analysis

In the analysis phase, detailed system requirements were gathered from key stakeholders, including **CCS students, faculty reviewers, and system administrators** of Gordon College, through consultations and review of existing research management practices. Issues in the current research submission and approval process were identified, such as fragmented submission methods, lack of centralized storage, limited revision tracking, and delays in multi-level approval.

Both **functional and non-functional requirements** were defined during this phase. Functional requirements included research paper

submission, revision and resubmission handling, multi-level approval workflows, role-based access control, and publication of approved research outputs. Non-functional requirements covered system security, performance, usability, data integrity, and accessibility across web and mobile platforms. The analysis phase ensured that the system requirements aligned with institutional research policies and the actual needs of the CCS community.

3.3.3 Design

Figure #. MERN Technologies Stack

The system was designed as a **web-based academic research management and moderation application** using the **MERN Stack architecture**, which includes **MongoDB, Express.js, React.js, and Node.js**. MongoDB was used for database management, Express.js and

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Node.js handled server-side logic and API services, while React.js was used to develop the interactive user interface.

The frontend design was styled using **Tailwind CSS** to ensure a responsive and consistent layout across devices. The system was developed as a **Progressive Web Application (PWA)**, allowing access through both web and mobile devices using standard browsers. This design ensures accessibility, scalability, and efficient management of research submission, review, and publication processes.

3.3.4 Development

During this development phase, the approved system design and requirements were translated into a functional application using the **MERN Stack**. The backend was developed using **Node.js** and **Express.js** to handle server-side logic, API endpoints, authentication, and the multi-level research approval workflow. **MongoDB** was used as the database to store user data, research metadata, extracted plain-text content, revision history, and approval records.

The frontend was developed using **React.js**, with **Tailwind CSS** applied to create a responsive and user-friendly interface. Core system features such as research submission, revision and resubmission handling,

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role-based access control, approval status tracking, and publication of approved research papers were implemented during this phase. The system was also configured as a **Progressive Web Application (PWA)** to ensure accessibility across both web and mobile devices.

Continuous testing and debugging were conducted throughout development to ensure that system functionalities operated correctly and met the defined requirements. This phase resulted in a fully functional prototype of ETHRIVE ready for testing and evaluation.

3.3.5 Testing

During this testing phase, the developed system was evaluated to ensure that all features functioned correctly and met the specified requirements. Functional testing was conducted to verify core features such as research submission, revision handling, approval workflows, and role-based access control.

User testing was also performed with selected CCS students and faculty members to identify errors, usability issues, and performance concerns. Feedback gathered during testing was used to fix issues and improve system reliability prior to deployment.

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3.3.6 Deployment and Implementation

During this deployment and implementation phase, the system was deployed using a **Virtual Private Server (VPS) droplet** hosted on **DigitalOcean**. The server environment was configured to support the MERN Stack, allowing the application to operate securely and efficiently in a production setting.

For file storage and access, **Microsoft Azure Blob Storage** was utilized to store research paper files securely. This cloud storage solution enabled reliable file handling, scalability, and controlled access to uploaded research documents. After deployment, the system was made accessible to CCS students and faculty members, ensuring proper configuration and stable operation for actual use.

3.3.7 Maintenance

The maintenance phase, the deployed system was monitored to ensure continuous and stable operation. This phase involved fixing reported bugs, applying minor updates, and improving system performance based on user feedback.

Regular checks were conducted on the application server and cloud storage to ensure data integrity and security. Maintenance activities ensured

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that the system remained functional, reliable, and aligned with the needs of CCS students and faculty members.

3.3.8 Post Evaluation

Post-evaluation was conducted, the implemented system was assessed based on feedback gathered from **CCS students and faculty instructors** after actual use. Evaluation focused on key criteria such as usability, functionality, performance, reliability, and user satisfaction using structured survey questionnaires.

The results of the post-evaluation were analyzed to determine the overall acceptability and effectiveness of the system. Feedback and identified issues served as a basis for recommending further enhancements and future improvements to better support academic research management and moderation.

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Chapter 4

SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations derived from the gathered data and analysis conducted in the study. The discussion focuses on the evaluation of the ETHRIVE platform in terms of usability, accessibility, efficiency, reliability, user satisfaction, and overall system acceptability based on the responses gathered during the pilot implementation conducted within the College of Computer Studies (CCS) of Gordon College.

4.1 Summary of Findings

This study aimed to design, develop, and evaluate **ETHRIVE: An Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack**. The proposed system was developed as a centralized academic research management and repository platform intended to support research submission, revision, approval, publication, and preservation processes across Gordon College.

For the purpose of implementation and evaluation, the pilot deployment of the system was conducted within the **College of Computer Studies**

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(CCS), which served as the initial testing environment and source of respondents for the study.

The study utilized a quantitative–descriptive research design and employed a researcher-modified usability questionnaire based on ISO 9241-11 usability principles and System Usability Scale (SUS)-related dimensions. Data were collected from fifty-three (53) respondents composed of selected student and faculty users who participated in the pilot evaluation of the system.

Based on the analysis and interpretation of data, the following findings were obtained:

1. **Ease of Use and Learnability** obtained a grand mean of **4.17 (Agree)**, indicating that respondents found the system easy to navigate, understand, and learn.
2. **Accessibility and Availability** received a grand mean of **3.98 (Agree)**, indicating that users were able to access the platform conveniently across available devices.
3. **Submission Efficiency** obtained a grand mean of **4.09 (Agree)**, demonstrating that the system improved and streamlined research submission activities.

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4. **Revision and Feedback Management** received a grand mean of **4.10 (Agree)**, showing that respondents found reviewer feedback, revision instructions, and revision monitoring effective and understandable.
5. **System Performance and Reliability** obtained the highest grand mean of **4.21 (Strongly Agree)**, indicating strong system responsiveness, operational stability, and dependable performance.
6. **User Satisfaction and Acceptance** received a grand mean of **4.08 (Agree)**, showing positive user perception and willingness to continue using and recommending the system.
7. **Problems Encountered**, interpreted using reverse scoring, obtained a grand mean of **4.40 (Strongly Agree)**, indicating that users experienced minimal technical and usability issues during system use.

Overall, the findings indicate that ETHRIVE demonstrated positive usability and acceptability outcomes during pilot implementation and showed potential as an institutional academic research management and repository platform for Gordon College.

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4.2 Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- 1.** ETHRIVE successfully provided a centralized and web-based academic research management platform intended to support research submission, revision, approval, publication, and preservation processes within Gordon College, with pilot implementation conducted within the College of Computer Studies (CCS).
- 2.** The respondents positively evaluated the system in terms of usability, accessibility, submission efficiency, revision management, performance, reliability, and user satisfaction, indicating that the proposed platform effectively addressed issues commonly associated with fragmented and manual research management processes.
- 3.** The system demonstrated strong operational performance and reliability, contributing to a stable and efficient user experience throughout research submission and moderation activities.
- 4.** The revision tracking and feedback management features improved transparency, communication, and monitoring between student researchers and academic reviewers.

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5. The reverse-scored evaluation of Problems Encountered confirmed that users experienced minimal operational and technical concerns during actual system usage.
6. The overall findings indicate that ETHRIVE is an acceptable and effective platform for supporting academic research governance and digital research management during pilot implementation and shows potential for wider institutional adoption.

Therefore, the study concludes that implementing a centralized research management platform such as ETHRIVE may contribute to improved efficiency, organization, accessibility, and preservation of academic research processes within Gordon College.

4.3 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The ETHRIVE platform may be considered for institutional adoption and phased implementation across Gordon College after further validation and deployment beyond the pilot phase.

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- 2.** Since the pilot implementation was limited to the College of Computer Studies, future implementation may include additional departments to evaluate system adaptability and institutional readiness.
- 3.** Future enhancements may include:
 - Automated notification mechanisms
 - PDF preview functionality
 - Mobile application optimization
 - Approval progress indicators
 - In-system communication features
 - Dark mode and accessibility improvements
- 4.** Additional security mechanisms, backup strategies, and audit capabilities may be integrated to strengthen data protection, reliability, and long-term preservation of research outputs.
- 5.** Future researchers are encouraged to conduct expanded evaluations involving larger populations and multiple academic departments to assess scalability, usability, and institutional acceptance.
- 6.** Future development may incorporate advanced capabilities such as:
 - plagiarism detection
 - citation validation
 - grammar checking

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- analytics dashboards
 - integration with external academic repositories
- 7.** Continuous maintenance, monitoring, and collection of user feedback are recommended to ensure that the system remains aligned with the evolving needs of students, faculty members, research coordinators, and institutional administrators.

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APPENDICES

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Appendix A – Relevant Source Code

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Appendix B – Evaluation Tool and Test Document

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Survey / Evaluation Questionnaire

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Section 1 of 10

ETHRIVE: An Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack

This survey aims to gather feedback on the **usability, effectiveness, and acceptability** of the web-based academic research management and moderation system. The questionnaire is designed to assess user experience, system performance, and areas for improvement based on actual system use.

There are **two versions of this survey**: one for **students** who submit research papers and another for **faculty instructors** who review and approve research submissions. All responses will be kept confidential and used solely for academic research purposes.

Consent Form

In compliance with **Republic Act No. 10173, the Data Privacy Act of 2012**, this study guarantees the protection of your personal data in accordance with legal provisions. This law safeguards the privacy of communication and ensures that any collected data will adhere to these standards to maintain your trust and confidence.

By proceeding with this survey, you acknowledge that:

You have read and understood the purpose and nature of the survey.

You agree to participate voluntarily.

You understand that your responses will remain confidential.

Agree

DEMOGRAPHICS

Under this section, provide personal information based on the statements below.

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DEMOGRAPHICS

Under this section, provide personal information based on the statements below.

Name (Optional)

Short answer text
.....

Age *

- 18-27
- 28-37
- 38-47
- 48-55
- 55+

Sex *

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other:

Programs *

1. Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT)
2. Bachelor of Science in Computer Science (BSCS)
3. Bachelor of Science in Entertainment and Media Computing (BSEMC)
4. Other Programs from other Departments (CBA, CHTM, CAHS, and CEAS)

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Year Level *

1. 1st Year
2. 2nd Year
3. 3rd Year
4. 4th Year

After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 2 of 10

SCREENING QUESTIONS

These questions are designed to determine if the respondent qualifies for the research.

Experience using the system: *

- First time
- Occasional user
- Frequent user

Device primarily used to access the system: *

- Laptop/Desktop
- Smartphone
- Tablet

Purpose of using the system: *

- Research paper submission / revision
- Research paper review / approval
- Viewing or searching research papers
- Other:

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Section 3 of 10

INSTRUCTIONS

Please rate your level of agreement with the following statements based on your experience. Use the scale below:

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Agree
- 4 - Strongly Agree

Ease of Use and Learnability

Description (optional)

The system is easy to navigate. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I can easily understand how to use the system. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The instructions provided in the system are clear and understandable. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

Learning how to submit my research paper was easy. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

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The interface layout is user-friendly. *

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly Agree

After section 3 Continue to next section

Section 4 of 10

Accessibility and Availability

Description (optional)

The system can be accessed anytime using available devices. *

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly Agree

The system works properly on the device I commonly use. *

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly Agree

The system is accessible whenever needed. *

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 Strongly Agree

After section 4 Continue to next section

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Section 5 of 10

Submission Efficiency

Description (optional)

Uploading my research paper is simple and convenient. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The system helps me complete submission tasks quickly. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

Using the system saves time compared to manual submission. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The submission process is organized and efficient. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The system clearly indicates whether my paper was successfully submitted. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

After section 5 Continue to next section

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Section 6 of 10

Revision and Feedback Management

Description (optional)

Reviewer feedback is clearly presented in the system. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I can easily identify the revisions required for my research paper. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The resubmission process is easy to perform. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The system helps me track the status of my paper during revisions. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

Revision instructions are easy to understand. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

After section 6 Continue to next section

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Section 7 of 10

System Performance and Reliability

Description (optional)

The system responds quickly during submission and revision activities. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The system functions smoothly while I use it. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The system performs reliably during research submission tasks. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The system properly records submitted research papers. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

After section 7 Continue to next section

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Section 8 of 10

User Satisfaction and Acceptance

Description (optional)

I am satisfied with the ETHRIVE system. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The system improves the research submission process. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

The system reduces confusion during research approval and revision. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I would recommend ETHRIVE to other students. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

I would continue using the system for future research activities. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

After section 8 Continue to next section

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Section 9 of 10

Problems Encountered ⌵ ⋮

Description (optional)

I encountered difficulties while submitting or revising my paper. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

Technical issues affected my experience while using the system. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

After section 9 Continue to next section ⌵

Section 10 of 10

Questions ⌵ ⋮

Description (optional)

What problems did you encounter while using the system?

Long answer text

⋮

What features should be improved in ETHRIVE? *

Long answer text

What additional features would you like the system to have? *

Long answer text

Other comments or suggestions *

Long answer text

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Business Model Canvas

**GORDON COLLEGE
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COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES**
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

Key Partners

- Gordon College
- Research Development and Community Extension Services
- College of Computer Studies Community
- Azure Cloud Storage
- Zenodo/DOI services and academic indexing partners
- Gemini AI

Key Activities

- Ingest, moderate, and publish papers (metadata, tagging, departments)
- Paper PDF Processing

Key Resources

- Centralized Database (MongoDB)
- Unified File Storage (Azure)
- Responsive Design (Mobile-first) thru PWA
- Moderation System

Value Proposition

- Single platform for all academic outputs and research
- Make gordon college research discoverable and accessible
- Support student research development
- Maintain academic standards thru Quality control through role-based access and moderation
- AI assistant and AI Paper Chat

Customer Relationship

- Self-serve onboarding; clear preview-to-subscribe upsell in-reader
- Proactive notifications (new papers, Top author's, Most Viewed/Read papers)

Channels

- Web app (PWA) via campus portals and department sites
- Social media and academic groups
- On-Campus Promotions

Customer Segments

- Students(undergrad/grad) needing research access and citation-ready papers
- Faculty/instructors and researchers (authors, reviewers, advisors)
- Research offices, departments, and libraries (institutional buyers)
- Admins and super-admins managing content, metadata, and policy
- External scholars and practitioners seeking local/regional studies

Cost Structure

- Cloud Hosting
- Potential DOI/metadata service costs
- Storage Expansion
- AI API key Subscription

Revenue Streams

- Individual subscriptions (monthly/annual) for full-text+download & AI features
- Day pass / pay-per-download microtransactions (Limited of 2 downloads for free user's)
- Institutional Funding

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Simplified Validation Board

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	EXPERIMENT 1	EXPERIMENT 2
Customer Segment	Cater only the 3rd and 4th Year CCS Students.	Cater Gordon College RDCES, CCS Faculties, and 3rd and 4th Year CCS Students
Problem	Limited access to academic resources for students.	Inefficient management and access to academic resources for all stakeholders.
Solution	Develop a student focused platform for accessing and archiving academic documents	Develop a comprehensive platform that addresses the needs of RDCES, CCS faculty, and 3rd and 4th year CCS students.
Experiment	Develop a comprehensive platform that addresses the needs of 3rd and 4th year CCS students.	Develop a comprehensive platform that addresses the needs of RDCES, CCS faculty, and 3rd and 4th year CCS students.
Success Criteria	At least 70% of surveyed 3rd and 4th year CCS students report improved access to academic resources.	At least 60% of surveyed faculty and students indicate improved efficiency in managing and accessing academic resources.
Result	Students find the platform beneficial, feedback indicates a need for expanded functionality that accommodates a broader range of academic users and features.	All user segments report that the platform significantly enhances resource management, document accessibility, and administrative workflow, validating its effectiveness.
Action	PIVOT to include additional user segments.	PURSUE the comprehensive platform development and full implementation.

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Appendix C – Sample Input/Output Reports

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Application Screenshots

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Appendix D – User Manual / User Guide

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Appendix E – Data Matrix

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Appendix F – Others

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**Team Activity and Progress
Narrative Report**

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Recommendation for Presentation

**GORDON COLLEGE
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Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

GORDON COLLEGE
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Olongapo City

ITP411: CAPSTONE PROJECT 1

RECOMMENDATION FOR RESEARCH PRESENTATION

**ETHRIVE: An Electronic These and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange
Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack**

By:

Del Rosario, Jomarie

**In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

has been examined and is recommended for

**I
RESEARCH PRESENTATION**

MENARD MANLAPAZ

Project Adviser's Name and Signature

Digitally Signed By

Menard Manlapaz

Date: 2025.04.05

12:13:20 +08:00

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OLONGAPO CITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

GORDON COLLEGE
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Olongapo City

ITP411: CAPSTONE PROJECT 1

RECOMMENDATION FOR 1st RESEARCH PRESENTATION

**ETHRIVE: An Electronic These and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange
Platform for Gordon College using MERN Stack**

By:

Del Rosario, Jomarie

**In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

has been examined and is recommended for

1st RESEARCH PRESENTATION

MENARD MANLAPAZ

Project Adviser's Name and Signature

Digitally Signed By

Menard Manlapaz

Date: 2025.05.03

12:13:20 +08:00

**GORDON COLLEGE
OLONGAPO CITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

GORDON COLLEGE
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Olongapo City

ITP411: CAPSTONE PROJECT 1

RECOMMENDATION FOR 2nd RESEARCH PRESENTATION

**ETHRIVE: An Electronic These and Higher Research
Information Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College
using MERN Stack**

By:

Del Rosario, Jomarie M.

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

has been examined and is recommended for
2nd RESEARCH Presentation

Mr. Menard Manlapaz

Project Adviser's Name and Signature

Digitally Signed By

Menard Manlapaz

Date: 2025.07.05

12:13:20 +08:00

Ms. Denise Lou Punzalan, MSCS

Beneficiary's Name and Signature

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info.ccs@gordoncollege.edu.ph
www.gordoncollegeccs.edu.ph

Gordon College CCS

Olongapo City

**GORDON COLLEGE
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Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

Final Defense Form

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Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

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COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Olongapo City

ITP411: CAPSTONE PROJECT 1

RECOMMENDATION FOR FINAL DEFENSE PRESENTATION

**ETHRIVE: An Electronic These and Higher Research
Information Vault Exchange Platform for Gordon College
using MERN Stack**

By:

Del Rosario, Jomarie M.

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

Digitally Signed By _____ has been examined and is recommended for
Menard Manlapaz _____ Final Defense Presentation

Date: 2025.09.30
12:13:20 +08:00

Mr. Menard Manlapaz

Project Adviser's Name and Signature

Ms. Denise Lou Punzalan, MSCS

Beneficiary's Name and Signature

Mr. Reynaldo Bautista Jr.

Coordinator's Name and Signature

Mr. Russel John U. Minimo

End User's Name and Signature

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Gordon College CCS

Olongapo City

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Photo Documentation of Implementation

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ACM Journal Article

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Curriculum Vitae

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COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES**
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

ERLINDA C. ABARINTOS, DIT

CONTACT

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abarintos.erlinda@gordoncollege.edu.ph

EDUCATION

Doctor of Information Technology

- St. Linus University

PHD-Technology Management (Acad units)

- Technological University of the Philippines

Master in Public Administration

- Ramon Magsaysay Technological University

Master in Engineering Maj in Computer Engineering (Acad Units)

- Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila

BS in Electronics and Communication Engineering

- Mapua Institute of Technology

ACCOMPLISHMENT

- Animahenasyon 2022 and 2023 Pre-Selection Judge
- 2021 Gawad Edukasyon Winner – Project Leader
- ALCU R3 Research Colloquium – Best Research Presenter
- Olongapo City LGU Service Awardee
- Board of Adviser, PSITE Region 3
- Fellow of Royal Institute of Information Technology (FRIIT)
- Outstanding IT Educator of the Year 2018
- JEDI (Java Education and Development Initiative) Champion

CURRENT WORK

Vice President for Administration and Finance [Job Title]

January 2018 – present

- Gordon College

CCS (College of Computer Studies) Dean

June 2001 – present

- Gordon College

AFFILIATION

Association of Computing Education Deans and Program Heads, Inc (ACEDPH)

- Treasurer / Public Information Officer

Philippine Society of Information Technology Educators Region III (PSITE Central Luzon)

- Honorary Member / Past President

Association of Local Colleges and Universities – Commission on Accreditation (ALCU – COA)

- Program Accreditor for Information Technology and Computer Engineering

abarintos
Digitally signed by
Abarintos Erlinda Casela
Date: 2025.03.17 20:17:36
+08'00'

**GORDON COLLEGE
OLONGAPO CITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES**
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

RONNIE DIONELO LUY

Assistant Professor 1

25 years in Teaching Profession

EDUCATION

ST. LINUS UNIVERSITY
Master in Information Technology
2013-2015 (Graduated)

ATENEO INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY INSTITUTE
Master of Science in Information Technology
2003-2005 (CAR)

MAPUA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY
Master of Science in Computer Engineering
2001-2002 (academic units)

PAMANTASAN NG LUNGSOD NG MAYNILA
Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering
1993-1998 (Graduated)

PROFILE

**MASTER IN INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY**

**BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN
COMPUTER ENGINEERING**

CONTACT ME

- (+63) 956 7146657
- luy.ronnie@gordoncollege.edu.ph
assistantdean.ccs@gordoncollege.edu.ph
- Dinalipuhan, Bataan
- December 29, 1976

CERTIFICATE

**CIVIL SERVICE PASSER
(PROFESSIONAL)**

WORK EXPERIENCE

GORDON COLLEGE
Assistant Dean, College of Computer Studies
(2018 - present)
BSIT Program Chair, College of Computer Studies
(2023 - present)
BSEMC Program Chair, College of Computer Studies
(2019 - 2021)
BSCS Program Chair, College of Computer Studies
(2016 - 2018)
Full-Time Instructor
(2016)

COLUMBAN COLLEGE
Dean, College of Computer Studies
(2010 - 2014)
Associate Dean, College of Computer Studies
(2003 - 2010)
Program Chair, College of Computer Studies
(2000 - 2003)
Full-Time Instructor
(2000 - 2016)
Part-Time Instructor
(1999 - 2000)

**GORDON COLLEGE
OLONGAPO CITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

REYNALDO G. BAUTISTA JR.

CCS-CESU COORDINATOR
Years in Teaching 5

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT

MASTER OF SCIENCE IN COMPUTER SCIENCE
President Ramon Magsaysay State University

BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN COMPUTER INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY
Columban College

INDUSTRY EXPERIENCE / EMPLOYMENT HISTORY

INSTRUCTOR I
August 2019 - Present
Gordon College

NETWORK ADMINISTRATOR / PURCHASER
July, 2005 - February, 2014
IDESS Interactive Technologies, Inc.

SOFTWARE TESTER \ DATA ENCODER
December, 2004 - July, 2005
IDESS Interactive Technologies, Inc.

COURSES HANDLED IN CLASS

- PC Troubleshooting with Basic Electronics
- Introduction to Human Computer Interaction
- Networking I

RESEARCH AND PUBLICATION

- Inventory Management and Monitoring System Using Progressive Web Application Framework
- CommuniServe: A Web-based Barangay Management System for the Barangays of Olongapo Using Progressive Web Framework
- Optimizing Veterinary Clinic: A PHP and MariaDB Powered Public Information Website and Inventory Management System
- FRENCHIE (Frenchtoss Clothing Co. Inventory and POS Management with Barcode System)
- Baking on the go: A cake Customization application for residents of Colo, Dinalupihan, Bataan

COMMUNITY EXTENSION

Resource Speaker

Digital Literacy: Empowering Minds in the Digital Era
March 6, 2024
Gordon Heights National High School

Code Connect: Bridging Communities through Basic Coding and Programming Skills
January 18, 2024
Sta Rita Senior High School

CONTACT

Phone
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Website
gordoncollege.ccs.edu.ph

Address
P6 Adama St., New Cabalan, Olongapo City, 2200

CERTIFICATE

NCII COMPUTER SYSTEMS SERVICES
Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA)

EXPERTISE

**GORDON COLLEGE
OLONGAPO CITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES**
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology

PROFILE

**BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY**
**MASTER OF SCIENCE IN
COMPUTER SCIENCE**

CONTACT ME

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programcoordinator.oct@gordoncollege.edu.ph
ccs.rapu@gordoncollege.edu.ph
- Sta. Rita, Olongapo City
- April 28, 1999

CERTIFICATIONS

**CIVIL SERVICE ELIGIBILITY (HONOR
GRADUATE ELIGIBILITY)**
**NCIII VISUAL GRAPHICS DESIGN
CISCO INSTRUCTOR LEVEL
CREDENTIAL**

DENISE LOU BORCELIS PUNZALAN

Instructor I

5 years in Teaching Profession

**RESEARCH AND
PUBLICATIONS**

**ERECORDS: A RECORDS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
USING PROGRESSIVE WEB FRAMEWORK FOR A
BARANGAY**

Authors: Denise Lou B. Punzalan, Nemia Galang
Published: *Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Education and
Technology (APJAET)* July 2022
P-ISSN 2815-245X E- ISSN 2815-2468

**BLUEHIRE: A BLUE-COLLAR JOB HIRING PLATFORM
FOR ON-CALL JOBS IN OLONGAPO CITY USING
CONTENT-BASED FILTERING AND VUE.JS
FRAMEWORK**

Authors: Haidee Hidocos, Jezreel Joshua Martin,
Roy Gopez Jr.
Adviser/Co-Author: Denise Lou B. Punzalan
Published: *Central Lens Journal*
Volume 2, Issue 2 / May 2023 / ISSN 2945-428X

**XMTS: A WEB-BASED ONLINE SHOP USING PHP
AND PROGRESSIVE WEB FRAMEWORK
AUTHORS: ERIS MENDOZA**

Authors: Eris Mendoza
Adviser/Co-Author: Denise Lou B. Punzalan
Published: *Central Lens Journal*
Volume 2, Issue 2 / May 2023 / ISSN 2945-428X

**GIZMOS AND LANGUAGE: A TOP-DOWN ROLE
PLAYING GAME FOR BASICS OF PROGRAMMING
USING UNITY**

Authors: Romeo John Perez
Adviser/Co-Author: Denise Lou B. Punzalan
Published: *Central Lens Journal*
Volume 1, Issue 2 / May 2023 / ISSN 2945-428X

**LEARNERS' ACADEMIC MANAGEMENT PORTAL
FOR HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN
CENTRAL LUZON**

Authors: Erlinda S. Casela – Abarintos, Melner Balce,
Loudel Manaloto, Kenneth Bautista, Denise Lou Punzalan,
Joseph Angelo Pusing, Sharmaine Manuel
Published: *BIGKIS*,
Volume 5, Issue 2023 / 2023 / EISSN 2945-3992

CCS COMPUTING RESEARCH JOURNAL

Authors: Erlinda S. Casela – Abarintos, Denise Lou Punzalan
Published: *Journal*
Volume 5, Issue No. 1 / 2024 / ISSN 2362-8154

**GORDON COLLEGE
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PROFILE

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- Sta. Rita, Olongapo City
- April 28, 1999

CERTIFICATIONS

**CIVIL SERVICE ELIGIBILITY (HONOR
GRADUATE ELIGIBILITY)**
NCIII VISUAL GRAPHICS DESIGN
**CISCO INSTRUCTOR LEVEL
CREDENTIAL**

**DENISE LOU
BORCELIS
PUNZALAN**

Instructor I

5 years in Teaching Profession

EDUCATION

**PRESIDENT RAMON MAGSAYSAY STATE
UNIVERSITY - IBA CAMPUS**
*Master of Science in Computer Science
(2020 - 2022)*

GORDON COLLEGE
*Bachelor of Science in Information Technology
(2015 - 2019)*

WORK EXPERIENCE

GORDON COLLEGE
*Program Chair, Associate in Computer Technology
(2021 - present)*
*Research Coordinator, College of Computer Studies
(2022 - present)*
*Full-Time Instructor
(2019 - present)*

PROFESSIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

**ASSOCIATION OF COMPUTING EDUCATION OF
DEANS AND PROGRAM HEADS (ACED.PH)**
*Active Member
(2021 - present)*

**PHILIPPINE SOCIETY OF INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY EDUCATORS (PSITE-CL) -
CENTRAL LUZON CHAPTER**
*Active Member
(2019 - present)*

**INSTITUTIONAL
ORCRANIZATIONS**

**GORDON COLLEGE ALUMNI ASSOCIATION INC.
(GCAAI)**
*Member, Working Committee
(2022 - present)*

GORDON COLLEGE FACULTY ASSOCIATION
*Member
(2019 - present)*

**GORDON COLLEGE EMPLOYEES CONSUMER
COOPERATIVE**
*Member, Working Committee
(2022 - present)*

MENARD MANLAPAZ

SOFTWARE ENGINEER /
FULL - STACK DEVELOPER

+63 976 052 5169
menardmanlapaz1@gmail.com
#134 Kessing Street New
Kalalake, Olongapo City

OBJECTIVE

My objective, aside to earn for living, is focused on gaining a work experience, acquiring new skills and to further develop my current skills by applying what I have learned.

SKILLS

Technical Skill

- Web Design
- Desktop System Development
- Back End Coding
- Front End Coding
- Problem-Solving
- Mobile app Development:
Android/iOS

Qualification

- Able to work under time pressure
- Ability to multi-task under pressure
- Knowledge in object oriented programming

EDUCATION

BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

Lyceum of Subic Bay
2015 - 2019

CERTIFICATES

- BEST SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN PROJECT - APRIL 2018
- GRAPHICS DESIGN NCII (TRIAL) - OCTOBER 2018
- 1ST RUNNER UP BACK-END CATEGORY (TORO) - OCTOBER 2018
- CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION BACK-END CATEGORY (TORO) - OCTOBER 2018
- CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION FRONT-END CATEGORY (TORO) - OCTOBER 2017
- CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION TORO-REGULATOR (RAITE) - AUGUST 2018
- CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION BACK-END CATEGORY CHAMPIONSHIP ROUND (TORO) - FEBRUARY 3
- CERTIFICATE OF SECURITY AWARENESS - APRIL 2022

EXPERIENCE

SOFTWARE ENGINEER - ALPHA GAMING ARCHA, PASAY

04/2024 - Present

- Utilized React Native, C#, .NET, and Unity to develop and architect feature-rich mobile applications.
- Led the development of a cross-platform (iOS and Android) mobile application with real-time functionalities, ensuring a seamless user experience on both web and mobile platforms.
- Additionally, spearheaded the creation of a crypto-based game, integrating blockchain technology for secure transactions and in-game assets, while focusing on user engagement and gameplay innovation.
- Responsible for feature development, code implementation, and maintaining high-performance standards across platforms.

SOFTWARE ENGINEER - OMADA ONE INC, CLARK

05/2023 - 01/2024

- Worked in a remote setup with a diverse cast of teams from Australia.
- Used Python, Flask, Django as Framework, Javascript, HTML/CSS, React, MongoDB, and TypeScript.
- Created and architected features based on the client's requirements
- responsible for creating a Marketing website application and mobile, involving tasks such as feature development, code implementation, and ensuring the real-time functionality of the Website

HIPE JAPAN, QUEZON CITY -SOFTWARE ENGINEER

10/2022 - 05/2023

- Worked in a remote setup with a diverse cast of teams from Japan.
- Used Python, Django as Framework, Websocket, Javascript HTML/CSS, Postgress, TypeScript, Node.js, Flutter, Dart, Vue.js, React, Node.js and FastAPI.
- Created and architected features based on the client's requirements
- responsible for creating a doctor appointment website and mobile application and mobile, involving tasks such as feature development, code implementation, and ensuring the real-time functionality of the Website

SOFTWARE ENGINEER - SKYDEV SOLUTIONS, SBFZ

05/2020 - 10/2022

- Used Python, Django, Websocket, Java, Javascript, HTML/CSS, Postgress, TypeScript, Node.js, Flutter, Dart, Vue.js and React.
- Created and architected features based on the client's requirements
- responsible for creating a live stream website and mobile application and mobile, involving tasks such as feature development, code implementation, and ensuring the real-time functionality of the Website

**GORDON COLLEGE
OLONGAPO CITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology**

Proponent Vitae

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**JOMARIE M.
DEL ROSARIO**

JDR

Contact

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Address
#33 Little Baguio I, East Bajac
Bajac, Olongapo City

Education

Accountancy and Business Management
Tapinac Senior High School
2020 - 2022

BS in Information Technology
Gordon College
2022 - Present

Technical Skills

- Basic Web Development (PHP, JS, HTML, CSS, MERN Stack)
- UI/UX Design Fundamentals
- Networking - Cisco Certified Network Associate (CCNA) - Certified
- MS Office Applications (Word, Excel, PowerPoint)
- Basic Database Concepts (MySQL, MongoDB)

Soft Skills

- Good Communication Skills
- Willingness to Learn
- Team Collaboration
- Time Management
- Positive Attitude

ABOUT ME

A 4th year BSIT student seeking an On-the-Job Training (OJT) / entry-level opportunity where I can apply my technical knowledge, develop professional skills, and gain real-world experience. Eager to learn, adaptable, and committed to contributing positively to the organization while enhancing my skills in the IT field.

EXPERIENCE

June 2022 to August 2022 | **Philippine Postal Corporation (PHILPOST) Encoder / Customer Service Assistant**
25 Arthur St, Olongapo City, 2200 Zambales

- Performed data encoding and record management
- Assisted customers with service inquiries

PROJECTS

ETHRIVE Web-app Capstone - Project Lead & Developer (solo)

- Developed a web-based platform for managing, archiving, and moderating student research outputs
- Designed features for electronic thesis submission and research information storage

NeighborLink Management Portal - Project Lead & Developer

- Created a community web application for HOA management and housing information
- Implemented features to help users view available homes within the community
- Focused on usability and organized data presentation

Practisease - Ui/Ux Developer

- Designed user interfaces for an OJT/Practicum management system
- Assisted in improving user experience for student requirement tracking
- Applied basic UI/UX principles to ensure clarity and ease of use

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Certificate of Proofreading